

Poor Livelihood Assets and Adaptive Strategies of the Riverbank Erosion Induced Charland People in Bangladesh: A Study on the Teesta Riverine Ecosystem

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ABSTRACT

Riverbank erosion in Bangladesh, intensified by climate change and fragile sandy soils, displaces thousands every year all over the country, leading to widespread human suffering and economic hardship. The present study is organised to assess the vulnerabilities and survival strategies of displaced households in Char Bidyananda, a separated village in the Teesta riverine ecosystem of Bangladesh. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the present study is primarily based on data gathered through structured interviews with 107 purposively selected displaced household heads, supplemented by observation, focus group discussions (FGDs), case studies, and informal interviews with key stakeholders. Research findings indicate that repeated displacements have caused severe financial, social, and health insecurities and have pushed them into a precarious state of plight. Significant losses include homesteads, crops, agricultural land, social care, and reported experiences of depression and anxiety. These losses illustrate multidimensional vulnerabilities, including physical, social, and motivational. The Pressure and Release (PAR) model is applied to analyse how these vulnerabilities arise from underlying root causes, dynamic pressures, and unsafe conditions. Charland people are compelled to engage in a range of adaptive strategies, including unpaid household chores and low-income-earning activities, in the absence of institutional support. The study recommends urgent community-based policy interventions, infrastructure development, vocational training, and sustainable livelihood initiatives to reduce vulnerability and strengthen household resilience.

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1. Introduction

Climate-induced displacement has emerged as one of the most pressing development and humanitarian challenges of the twenty-first century. The World Bank's Groundswell projections indicate that by 2050, well over 216 million individuals across six global regions may become internal climate migrants, with South Asia expected to contribute roughly 40 million of these displacements (Rigaud et al., 2018; Clement et al., 2021). This region's high population density, significant reliance on agriculture, and prevalent poverty exacerbate susceptibility to erosion-related displacement and disruption of livelihoods (Mukherjee et al., 2020; Bhuiyan, 2017). The extensive river systems of South Asia, specifically the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna basins, sustain millions of smallholder farmers who depend significantly on fertile floodplain soils for their livelihoods and revenue. Nonetheless, recurrent erosion, flooding, and sedimentation cycles persistently threaten these agricultural areas and settlements (Hossain, 2023; Sajjad, 2024).

In South Asia, nations like Bangladesh, India, and Nepal exhibit comparable geophysical susceptibilities because of their deltaic and alluvial terrains. The Ganges–Brahmaputra–Meghna (GBM) basin, among the largest transboundary river systems worldwide, sustains approximately 700 million people, making it one of the most densely populated and ecologically challenged basins globally (Mukherjee et al., 2020; Gain & Giupponi, 2015). Seasonal flooding, sediment deposition, and persistent riverbank erosion significantly impact agricultural livelihoods and the viability of settlements throughout the region. The Brahmaputra River in India erodes almost 8,000 hectares of land each year, displacing nearly 2 million individuals in Assam (Chakraborty et al., 2020; Gogoi et al., 2021). Recurrent flooding and erosion along Nepal's Koshi River result in

substantial land loss and frequent displacement of vulnerable households in the low-lying Terai plains (MoFE, 2021). These trends demonstrate that erosion-induced displacement has emerged as a collective climatic and livelihood catastrophe throughout South Asia's principal river basins.

Bangladesh, situated at the downstream convergence of several significant rivers, is especially vulnerable. The nation is extensively acknowledged as one of the most climate-vulnerable countries globally (Huq & Rabbani, 2011; IPCC, 2022). Riverbank erosion is considered one of its most enduring and detrimental natural disasters. Every year, the Teesta, Brahmaputra, Dharla, and Dudhkumer rivers in northern Bangladesh displace numerous families from their land and residences. The Kurigram Relief and Rehabilitation Centre reports that, each year, more than 3,000 families lose their homes due to ongoing erosion in the districts of Kurigram and Lalmonirhat (The Business Post, 2022). Riverbank erosion contributes to physical displacement and the degradation of productive resources, social networks, and livelihood security, thereby exacerbating poverty and marginalisation in rural communities (Alam, 2016; Hutton & Haque, 2003; Lein, 2000). Erosion-induced displacement results in significant socio-economic repercussions. Impacted households frequently forfeit agricultural land, housing, and work, concurrently enduring prolonged exclusion from social and institutional safety nets. These dynamics sustain enduring poverty, food insecurity, and social fragmentation (Islam & Rashid, 2011; Shetu et al., 2023; Hossain & Al Fahad, 2023; Ahmad & Afzal, 2023). The repercussions of these displacements go beyond the immediate loss of land; they signify accumulated vulnerabilities that exacerbate the

structural marginalisation of populations affected by erosion. The Teesta Riverine ecosystem in northern Bangladesh distinctly illustrates these vulnerabilities. Char Bidyananda, an isolated settlement within Bidyananda Union, is among the worst affected. The community experiences limited access to governmental services, high-quality education, and opportunities for economic diversification. The lack of protection for embankments, flood-control infrastructure, and reliable early-warning systems increases communities' vulnerability to environmental hazards. Consequently, a cycle of instability and reliance continually uproots families, leaving them with few prospects for enduring recovery.

Empirical studies have underscored the adaptive strategies of erosion-impacted households in Bangladesh, encompassing income diversification, seasonal movement, small-scale commerce, and the mobilisation of social networks (Barua et al., 2019; Rahman & Gain, 2020; Islam & Hossain, 2020; Paul et al., 2021; Shamim et al., 2025). Nevertheless, the majority of research has been on generic livelihood adaptations to floods or cyclones, with insufficient emphasis on the distinct survival strategies and vulnerability pathways of erosion-displaced households in the Teesta basin. A significant research gap persists regarding how these households navigate survival, reconstruct livelihoods, and achieve long-term resilience following repeated displacement.

This study aims to assess the vulnerability and survival strategies of households displaced by riverbank erosion in the Teesta riverine ecosystem of Bangladesh. Specifically, it seeks to (i) analyse the forms and drivers of vulnerability faced by displaced households and (ii) examine the adaptive and survival strategies

they utilise to mitigate both immediate and long-term livelihood losses. This work enhances the understanding of the human aspects of climate-induced displacement and resilience in one of the most erosion-prone regions of the South Asian floodplain.

2. Methodology

The study employed a mixed-method research design grounded in the pragmatist paradigm, which provides the core philosophical basis for mixed-method inquiry (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010; Morgan, 2007). Pragmatism allows researchers to integrate quantitative data with qualitative insights to understand complex real-life issues. Guided by this approach, the study combined numerical evidence with contextual narratives to produce a comprehensive understanding of riverbank-erosion-induced displacement, livelihood insecurity, and household vulnerability.

Char Bidyananda, a geographically fragile *Charland* located in Bidyananda union of Rajarhat Upazila under Kurigram district in northwestern Bangladesh, was purposively selected as the study site due to its high exposure to erosion of the Teesta River, recurrent displacement, and structural marginality. According to the Union Parishad Report (2018), the total population of Char Bidyananda comprises 431 households, of which 31 experienced riverbank-erosion-induced displacement at least once in their lifetime and were therefore considered eligible for inclusion. The study adopted purposive sampling and selected 107 households, representing 24.8% of the total household population. Mathematically, the sampling fraction was calculated as $n/N = 107/431 \approx$

0.248, ensuring that nearly one-fourth of the total households were included, which strengthened representativeness. Furthermore, maximum-variation criteria were applied to ensure diversity across socio-economic categories, land-loss severity, age cohorts, and spatial clusters within the *char*. The unit of analysis was the displaced household, represented primarily by the household head; in cases of the household head's absence, the second household decision-maker served as the respondent.

Data collection involved multiple complementary tools to ensure triangulation and validity. A structured household survey generated quantitative data on socio-economic characteristics, erosion impacts, livelihood assets, and coping mechanisms. To enrich the understanding of lived experiences, two focus group discussions (one with a male group and one with female, male, and elected local leaders) and three in-depth case studies were conducted,

exploring collective vulnerabilities, gendered experiences, and sequential displacement histories. Four key informant interviews with the Union Parishad Secretary, two elected members, and one NGO worker were included to capture institutional perspectives, governance challenges, and local-level responses. Additionally, direct field observations were conducted to document settlement patterns, embankment conditions, housing types, erosion scars, and mobility constraints, thereby helping to validate and contextualise the quantitative findings. Several procedural measures were undertaken to ensure the authenticity and credibility of subjective information, including methodological triangulation across surveys, FGDs, KIIs, and observations; real-time probing during interviews; consistency checks across respondent groups; enumerator training to minimise bias; and community validation sessions with long-term residents.

Figure 1: Study Area

Data processing and analysis were conducted using SPSS, Microsoft Excel, and Microsoft Word. Quantitative data were subjected to descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, cross-tabulations, and composite indices to assess socioeconomic vulnerability and livelihood outcomes. Qualitative information from FGDs, KIIs, case studies, and observations was analysed using thematic content analysis, in which emergent themes were compared with quantitative patterns to identify convergence, divergence, and explanatory insights. Data interpretation in this study was guided by the PAR model, which systematically traces how vulnerability evolves from underlying root causes through dynamic pressures to unsafe conditions. This framework was applied to explain the progression of risk and to assess how riverbank-erosion-induced displacement affects the livelihood assets and adaptive capacity of the affected households. All tables, figures, charts, and textual descriptions were prepared using Microsoft Word and Excel to ensure clarity, consistency, and structured presentation.

3. Result and Discussion

Socioeconomic Profile of Charland Households

A socioeconomic profile of households provides a comprehensive picture of their lives, including income, education, and living conditions. It helps to better understand their situation.

The socioeconomic profile of Char Bidyananda reveals significant disparities in educational attainment among its residents.

Approximately 77.5% of the population falls into the illiterate category, with a notable gender difference; 50.5% of males and 27.1% of females are illiterate. Only 1.9% of respondents completed graduate, secondary, or higher secondary education. Primary completion is 16.8% (11.2% males, 5.6% females). Poverty, poor infrastructure, weak communication, adverse weather, and family reluctance cause high dropout rates, pushing children into fieldwork from an early age (Table 1). The present findings are consistent with previous research. Islam and Nurullah (2021) reported an illiteracy rate of 76.4% among displaced parents, while Barua et al. (2019) found that 42.6% of respondents had education below the primary level. Similarly, Hossain (2015) documented an illiteracy rate of 44%.

Only 0.9% of households fall into the rich category (>7.5 acres), 4.7% into the average category (2.5–7.5 acres), and 5.6% into the poor category (1–2.5 acres). The largest share, 37.4%, are marginal farmers possessing less than one acre of land and are often dependent on leasing arrangements such as *Adi* (*Adi* is a land leasing system where the tenant agrees to give a fixed portion of the harvest or its value to the landowner in exchange for using the land for a set period), *Contact* (the *Contact* system is a land lease where tenants pay a fixed amount for temporary use, returning the land after the term without reimbursement), or *Bondhok* (*Bondhok* is a temporary land transfer in which the tenant pays the landowner a fixed sum and uses the land until the loan is repaid). This unequal land distribution significantly contributes to the village's socio-economic challenges.

Table 1: Socioeconomic profile of displaced households

Educational status		Total Households = 107	
		(N)	(%)
Illiterate		83	77.5
	Primary	18	16.8
Literate	Secondary	2	1.9
	Higher Secondary	2	1.9
	Graduation	2	1.9
Landownership Pattern			
Category	Land (in acres)		
Rich	>7.50	1	0.9
Average	>2.50 - ≤7.50	5	4.7
Poor	>1.00 - ≤2.50	6	5.6
Marginal	≤1.00	40	37.4
Landless	With Homestead	55	51.4
Monthly household income			
Lower	1000-8000	84	78.5
Lower middle	8001-14000	13	12.1
Middle	14001-20000	6	5.6
Upper	>20000	4	3.7

Most households in Char Bidyananda have low incomes: 78.5% earn 1,000–8,000 BDT per month, 12.1% earn 8,001–14,000 BDT, and very few exceed 14,000 BDT. Specifically, 79.4% of these households had only one source of income, and income was constrained by poverty, river erosion, poor infrastructure, limited capital, low skills, and limited financial access.

Case#1

Rahima (resident of the Char Bidyannanda, 28) stated, *“I earn 250 TK per day. The family does not function effectively with it. During the rainy season, when the char becomes inundated, opportunities for paid labour are significantly reduced. Also, not enough funds are allocated for family emergencies. We always confront financial challenges to fulfil fundamental family needs.”*

Housing is predominantly non-concrete (99.1%) with Corrugated Iron Sheets for walls and roofs, reflecting the need for flexible

structures due to riverbank erosion. Only 0.9% of houses are semi-concrete, and some have straw kitchens with jute walls.

Occupational Status of the Charland Households

In Char Bidyananda, domestic professions demonstrate considerable diversity, indicating varying degrees of livelihood security and adaptive capacity. Increased household income typically bolsters resilience and diminishes susceptibility to environmental and economic disturbances.

Table 2 indicates the occupational distribution of the studied displaced households. Among male family heads (n=70), a significant majority (88.6%) depend on agricultural labour as their principal source of subsistence. A small percentage (4.3%) is involved in garment work, while only 1.4% work in NGOs, retail, religious service (Imam), or the military, or are unemployed owing to disability.

Table 2: Occupation of displaced households

Occupation of household		Total Households=107	
		n	%
Male Heads [N=70]	Agricultural Labourer	62	88.6
	NGO Workers (Instalment manager)	1	1.4
	Garment Workers	3	4.3
	Textile industry Clothing industry		
	Imam (Religious Leader)	1	1.4
	Shopkeeper	1	1.4
	Unemployment (Person with Disability)	1	1.4
	Service Holder (Military)	1	1.4
Total	70	100	
Female Heads [N=37]	Housewife	31	83.8
	Agricultural Labourer	2	5.4
	Service Holder (Elected member)	1	2.7
	Shopkeeper	2	5.4
	Beggar	1	2.7
Total	37	100	

In female-headed families (n=37), the majority (83.8%) identify as housewives, indicating minimal participation in formal or remunerated employment. A minor percentage engages in agricultural labour (5.4%), small-scale commerce (5.4%), local governing positions (2.7%), or resorts to begging (2.7%) for subsistence.

Displacement Status of the Charland Families

Riverbank erosion in the Kurigram district has forced many riparian people to migrate within and outside the riverbank erosion-prone areas. Some have relocated within the same village, seeking safety from the Teesta riverbank erosion displacement. The displaced households in Char Bidyananda have suffered from the loss of their original homestead and cultivable lands due to the frequent riverbank dislocation. Their

displacement experiences are categorised into four groups: 1-5 times, 6-10 times, 11-15 times, and more than 15 times (Figure 2). These circumstances have left them in precarious living conditions within their Charland habitats.

High-magnitude riverbank erosion and floods that occur in Charland areas are viewed as disastrous, as they inundate large areas and cause widespread damage to crops, livestock, and property as well as devastation to the life and livelihoods of the char-dwellers (Smith, 2013; Handmer et al., 2002; Paul, 1984; Brammer, 1990; Rasid, 1993; Few, 2003; Zaber et al., 2018; Islam & Nurullah, 2021). The field data reveal that a majority, 57% of households experienced 1-5 displacements, 24% faced 6-10 displacements, 9% endured 11-15 displacements, and 10% had to endure more than 15 displacements due to riverbank erosion.

Figure 2: Displacement times of the Charland families

4. Losses Due to Riverbank Erosion Displacement of the Households

After displacement, affected households face multifaceted losses encompassing physical, social, and motivational assets, all of which

originate from their pre-existing vulnerability. The erosion-induced destruction not only eliminates tangible resources but also disrupts community relations and undermines psychological resilience.

Table 3: Riverbank erosion displacement induced losses of displaced households

Types of Assets	Losses of households	N	%	Majority
Physical	Homeland	107	100	1 st
	Crops (nuts, potatoes, pulses, etc.)	99	92.5	2 nd
	Trees	96	89.7	3 rd
	Toilets	96	89.7	3 rd
	Collected hay	70	65.4	4 th
	Agricultural land	69	64.5	5 th
	House (without land)	33	30.8	6 th
	Animals (selling of cows, goats, ducks, chickens, etc.)	9	8.4	7 th
	Fishing grounds	6	5.6	8 th
	Road	6	5.6	9 th
	Furniture (tables, chairs, beds)	4	3.7	10 th
	Culvert	2	1.9	11 th
Jewellery	1	0.9	12 th	
Social	Social care	101	94.4	1 st
	Resilience	100	93.5	2 nd
	Damage to natural beauty	84	78.5	3 rd
	Psychological damage	61	57.0	4 th
	Competitiveness	74	69.1	5 th
	Community cohesion	59	55.1	6 th
	Social contact	54	50.1	7 th
	Social network	54	50.1	7 th
	Privacy of women	53	49.3	8 th
	Child dropout	37	34.8	9 th
Employment	36	33.6	10 th	

Types of Assets	Losses of households	N	%	Majority
	Security of children	36	33.6	10 th
	Liveable environment	35	32.7	11 th
	Cultural heritage	6	5.6	12 th
Motivational	Reluctance to relocate	70	65.4	1 st
	Loss hope	52	48.6	2 nd
	Depression and anxiety	19	17.8	3 rd
	Emotional stress	12	11.2	4 th

Physical Losses

Households in Char Bidyananda endure significant physical losses from riverbank erosion, with every assessed family (100%) having lost their homeland, which constitutes the essential foundation of their livelihood and identity. A significant majority also forfeit essential agricultural assets: 92.5% lose standing or harvested crops, and 89.7% lose trees and sanitation facilities (toilets). Furthermore, 65.4% indicate the loss of stored hay, while 64.5% see a reduction in agricultural land, hence threatening food and economic security. Additional substantial damages encompass the obliteration of residences (30.8%), coerced liquidation of cattle (8.4%), and the forfeiture of fishing territories (5.6%), thoroughfares (5.6%), furnishings (3.7%), culverts (1.9%), and jewels (0.9%). The physical losses arise from households' significant exposure to erosion-prone terrain, precarious housing, and reliance on riverine agriculture.

Social Losses

Social losses are significant, indicating a deterioration of community structure and social cohesion. A majority of families indicate a decline in social care (94.4%) and

community resilience (93.5%), signifying a breakdown of mutual support systems. Damage to the natural landscape (78.5%) has diminished community attachment and aesthetics, while 57% report psychological anguish resulting from social and environmental upheaval. Decreases in competitiveness (69.1%), community cohesion (55.1%), and both social interaction and networks (50.1%) demonstrate how displacement disrupts social capital. Moreover, the loss of women's privacy (49.3%), child school dropout rates (34.8%), unemployment (33.6%), and child insecurity (33.6%) illustrate the deterioration of household stability and protective measures. The decline of a habitable environment (32.7%) and the erosion of cultural heritage (5.6%) emphasise the social fragmentation caused by repeated displacement.

Motivational Losses

Motivational losses reflect the profound emotional and psychological burden of ongoing dislocation. Approximately 65.4% of households exhibit an unwillingness to relocate, indicative of emotional ties to ancestral land and apprehension regarding additional loss. Approximately 48.6% indicate a loss of hope, reflecting enduring despair stemming from the continuous cycle of

degradation and destitution. Mental health impacts are significant: 17.8% suffer from sadness and anxiety, while 11.2% endure prolonged emotional stress. These motivational deficits arise from persistent insecurity, instability in transient accommodations, and traumatic recollections of losing homes, possessions, and social connections. The cumulative impact diminishes adaptive capacity, resulting in households becoming discouraged and less inclined to reconstruct or seek new chances.

5. Assessment of the Progression of Vulnerability by PAR Model

The vulnerability of households in Char Bidyananda can be comprehensively explained through the PAR model developed by Blaikie et al. (2014). The model conceptualises disaster as the intersection of hazard and vulnerability, in which vulnerability itself emerges through a sequence of root causes, dynamic pressures, and unsafe conditions. This analytical framework helps trace how deep-seated social and structural inequalities transform a natural hazard like riverbank erosion into a disaster for local populations (Wisner et al., 2004).

5.1 Root Causes: Structural and Institutional Deficits

The root causes of vulnerability in Char Bidyananda are embedded in long-term socio-economic deprivation and political marginalisation. Households suffer from limited access to key livelihood assets such as capital, skilled labour, education, healthcare, and reliable transportation. The absence of

healthcare facilities—with the nearest community clinic located 2–3 km away—reflects systemic neglect of rural health infrastructure. Furthermore, geographic isolation, with the Teesta River acting as a physical barrier, exacerbates the social exclusion of Char Bidyananda. The community's limited connectivity to urban centres restricts access to employment, markets, and institutional supports (education, medical services, or government safety net programs). Similar patterns of spatial exclusion have been documented by Paul and Routray (2011), who observed that remoteness often leads to underinvestment and marginalisation in erosion-prone areas.

The lack of political representation and policy visibility constitutes another critical root cause. The absence of consistent governmental or NGO attention in Char Bidyananda aligns with what Blaikie et al. (2014) describe as the “political economy of vulnerability,” where marginalised rural communities remain invisible in policy discourse. According to the FGD participants, Char Bidyananda is generally perceived as a disaster-prone and underdeveloped area, which leads to government development projects being concentrated mainly on the mainland, leaving the char areas neglected. They also mentioned that many local residents still hold a strong traditional or religious belief that “riverbank erosion is God’s will.” As a result, there is little motivation to take preventive or adaptive measures. At the same time, economic instability and limited access to financial resources make it even more difficult for households to undertake such initiatives.

5.2 Dynamic Pressures: Weak Institutional and Adaptive Mechanisms

The dynamic pressures translate the structural root causes into more immediate vulnerabilities. In Char Bidyananda, the absence of embankments and flood barriers has intensified exposure to erosion. While embankments are often considered key mitigation structures in riverine Bangladesh (Gain et al., 2017), their uneven distribution and poor maintenance in peripheral villages contribute to heightened disaster risks. According to FGD participants, one of the most critical dynamic pressures in Char Bidyananda is the deficit in community training and preparedness, which severely undermines local adaptive capacity to cope with riverbank erosion and floods. They mention that most of the residents lack essential survival and adaptation skills, such as swimming, emergency evacuation, house relocation, and community-based erosion control techniques. In a highly flood-prone environment where river currents are strong, the inability to swim becomes a life-threatening constraint, particularly for women, children, and elderly residents. The absence of community-level training and early-warning mechanisms

further weakens household readiness and collective resilience. This finding aligns with Parvin and Shaw (2011), who found that inadequate disaster preparedness and limited community knowledge transfer significantly increase vulnerability to environmental shocks. Similarly, Paul and Routray (2011) found that inadequate institutional coordination and the absence of practical disaster management training heighten social fragility, transforming predictable hazards into livelihood crises.

Additionally, limited financial investment and inadequate institutional support from both governmental and non-governmental organisations reinforce the cycle of deprivation. The absence of sustained development interventions, such as infrastructural improvement, agricultural modernisation, and livelihood diversification, has trapped the village in what Cutter et al. (2012) describe as chronic vulnerability. This condition is further intensified by macro-level forces such as climate change, recurrent flooding, and soil fertility decline, gradually transforming persistent poverty into structural vulnerability (Birkmann et al., 2013).

Figure 3: Progression of Vulnerability by Pressure and Release (PAR) Model

5.3 Unsafe Conditions: Immediate Exposure and Fragile Livelihoods

At the micro level, unsafe conditions represent the visible, day-to-day manifestation of vulnerability produced by deeper structural and dynamic pressures. In Char Bidyananda, the combination of sandy soil composition, absence of vegetative cover, and proximity to the Teesta River creates an ecologically unstable environment that is highly susceptible to erosion. The lack of riparian vegetation removes natural barriers that could stabilise riverbanks and reduce soil collapse. Similar patterns were documented by Islam and Walkerden (2014), who identified the loss of tree cover and degradation of floodplain ecosystems as key ecological drivers of erosion-induced vulnerability in northwestern Bangladesh.

Environmental insecurity is further compounded by the local economic structure. The community depends heavily on subsistence agriculture, and FGD participants reported that unregulated and unexpected

sand mining further aggravates environmental degradation. Illegal sand extraction destabilises the riverbed and intensifies hydraulic pressure, while unsustainable farming practices, such as mono-cropping and cultivation near the river edge, reduce soil cohesion and fertility. These feedback loops transform natural instability into chronic exposure. Field data also revealed that 57.0% of households have had to relocate two to five times in the past decade, depleting savings and assets each time.

Within the economic dimension of unsafe conditions, households' financial resilience is severely constrained. Most families operate under low- and irregular-income streams, leaving them unable to recover after displacement. The majority rely on high-interest informal loans to rebuild houses or purchase agricultural inputs, perpetuating a cycle of debt and dependency. Similar findings were reported by Hutton and Haque (2003),

who observed that erosion-induced displacement in Bangladesh's floodplains experiences persistent economic insecurity and reduced adaptive capacity due to livelihood instability. This condition aligns with Cutter and Finch (2008), who identified economic fragility as a core determinant of social vulnerability to natural hazards. Institutional inadequacies further intensify unsafe conditions. Weak early warning systems, poor disaster-preparedness training, and delayed responses reveal systemic governance gaps that turn recurring erosion and flooding into humanitarian crises. As Wisner et al. (2004) note, hazards become disasters when social systems fail to act effectively. Studies in Bangladesh support this: Mallick and Vogt (2014) show that limited institutional coordination hinders recovery, while Hutton and Haque (2003) observed that erosion-induced displaced people face economic insecurity and reduced adaptive capacity due to insufficient institutional assistance. These patterns align with Cutter and Finch (2008), who identify economic fragility as a core driver of social vulnerability.

The PAR model thus provides a holistic understanding of the vulnerability in Char Bidyananda. It explains how deep-rooted inequalities (limited assets, political marginalisation), when combined with dynamic forces (like flooding, poor governance, lack of preparedness), culminate in unsafe living conditions that are easily disrupted by hazards like riverbank erosion. When the hazard strikes, the "pressure" of accumulated vulnerability is "released" in the form of disaster, manifested through displacement, loss of land, and livelihood insecurity. The model underscores that riverbank erosion is not merely a physical hazard but a socially constructed disaster,

deeply shaped by development failures and governance neglect.

6. Survival Strategies of Displaced Households

Households that have been displaced as a result of riverbank erosion in Char Bidyananda implement a variety of strategies to adapt to their new circumstances. These strategies encompass the following: securing immediate shelter, engaging in both income-earning and unpaid agricultural work, seeking greater support from family members, dedicating additional time to their occupations, increasing community engagement, hunting for government and non-government job opportunities, and focusing on animal husbandry. In an effort to enhance their employment prospects, they also strive to acquire new local skills or refine existing ones.

Households in Char Bidyananda participate in a variety of activities, both paid and unpaid, both within and outside their residences, in order to confront the obstacles presented by riverbank erosion displacement. These activities are essential for the maintenance of stability and the provision of support for their families. Three categories of individuals typically provide support within a family: Household heads (primarily the father), females (primarily the mother), and children (son and daughter). In the village of Char Bidyananda, these support dynamics are frequently observed in solitary households.

In this study, it is found that male heads engage in diverse survival strategies that combine both unpaid familial contributions and income-generating activities. Universally (100%), household men maintain and provide

mental and emotional support to their families, demonstrating a gender role adaptation in post-displacement contexts where traditional divisions of labour become more fluid. A significant percentage of male heads (95.1%) also engage in child care, reflecting heightened engagement in domestic caregiving during crises. Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood, with 96.1% of male heads involved in the farming sector and 88.3% engaged in animal husbandry. This sustained reliance on agriculture persists even after displacement, despite reduced access to cultivable land and falling productivity. A very

limited share of households pursues fishing (6.8%) or handicraft-making (2.9%), illustrating the narrow range of alternative income opportunities available in erosion-affected and resource-scarce settings.

Regarding income-earning activities (IEAs), nearly three-quarters (74.8%) continue agricultural labour as their primary income source, while a minimal share (1.0%) holds government employment, and 5.8% work in non-government sectors, including garments or religious institutions to support their family economically (Table 4).

Table 4: Survival strategies of displaced households

Household-level survival strategies		Male heads [N=103/103]	
		n	%
Unpaid Familial Works	Helping with housework (cooking, elderly care and medication, house repairs, laundry, tube well area clean up, etc.)	103	100
	Child caring (feeding, changing diapers/clothes, bathing, meal preparation, health and medical care, etc.)	98	95.1
	Providing mental support (mental support, guidance, empathy, safe space, problem-solving, etc.)	103	100
	Shop keeping (daily essentials: non-perishables, biscuits, bananas, bread, tea, etc.)	2	1.9
	Agricultural work (planting, harvesting, weeding, repairing, pruning, cleaning equipment, storing agricultural products, etc.)	99	96.1
	Animal husbandry (shelter, feeding, concentration on disease prevention and reproduction, handling, etc.)	91	88.3
	Fishing (baiting hooks, hand and fishing, etc.)	7	6.8
	Handicrafts (fishing nets, bamboo products: winnowing fan (<i>kula</i>), <i>Dali</i> (indigenous carrier on head), <i>Duli</i> (indigenous rice container), etc.)	4	2.9
Income Earning Activities (IEAs)	Agricultural work (tilling, planting, spreading, spraying, weeding, harvesting, pruning, cleaning, repairing, storing agricultural products, etc.)	77	74.8
	Government jobs (military)	1	1.0
	Non-government jobs (garment workers, imam of mosque, etc.)	6	5.8

N.B.: Multiple responses

Within households, female heads play a crucial role in sustaining family resilience during crises as well as in normal times. All female

households (100%) are engaged in unpaid familial work, particularly housework, underscoring their central contribution to

household management. In addition to domestic responsibilities, a large proportion participate in animal husbandry (94.4%), vegetable cultivation (92.5%), childcare (97.2%), and elder care (85.0%). Moreover, all female heads (100%) provide mental and emotional support to their families during periods of hardship. A small share (1.9%) operates as shopkeepers, selling basic household commodities, while participation in income-earning activities remains minimal, only 4.7% of respondents are engaged in agricultural labour (Table 5). The findings of the study are empirically supported by the work of Bassar and Tasnuva (2017). They found that after floods, women play a vital role in recovery activities, engaging in soil carrying (8%), house repair and elevation (23%), homestead gardening (31%), poultry rearing (27%), and fence construction (11%).

Children also contribute to households through unpaid familial work, such as helping with housework (100%), engaging in agricultural work (88.7%), providing child

care (100%), and providing crucial mental support (100%). Additionally, sons (Only male children) contribute to the household income with income-earning activities, including agricultural work (15.6%) and non-governmental or NGO positions, such as garment work (3.1%). Furthermore, 9.3% of the children, consisting of 6 males and 3 females, work temporarily in paid garment jobs to contribute to their families. After completing each year of their secondary education, some of them relocate to urban areas to work and support both their families and themselves (Table 5). The results of this study are consistent with the empirical evidence reported by Kamal (2011), where he found that during the harvesting season, women and children (inactive labour force) come forward to support the family, and 41% of children in the 6-12 age group participated in the rearing of domestic animals.

Table 5: Survival strategies of displaced families

Household-level survival strategies		Female heads	
		[N=107/107]	
		n	%
Unpaid Familial Works	Housework (keeping house clean, cooking, washing clothes, gathering firewood/ hay, etc.)	107	100
	Animal husbandry (shelter and housing, feeding, nutrition management, etc.)	101	94.4
	Growing vegetables (cultivation, handling, care and collection of vegetables, etc.)	99	92.5
	Child caring (feeding, medicine, monitoring)	104	97.2
	Elder care (providing meals and medicine)	91	85.0
	Providing mental support (mental support, guidance, empathy, problem-solving, etc.)	107	100
	Shop keeping (daily essentials: non-perishables, biscuits, bananas, bread, tea, etc.)	2	1.9
	Agricultural work	40	37.4
Income Earning	Agricultural work (land acquisition, paddy planting, paddy harvesting, potato planting, maize planting, almond planting,	5	4.7

Activities (IEAs)	wheat work, onion, garlic, chilli works, dal (<i>Kalai</i>) lifting and drying, etc.)	Children [N=97]	
Unpaid	Helping with housework	97	100
Familial	Agricultural work	86	88.7
Works	Child caring (feeding, bathing, sleeping etc.)	97	100
	Providing mental support	97	100
	Animal husbandry	32	33
Income	Agricultural work (planting and harvesting)	10	15.6
Earning	Garments work (quality checker of clothes, monitoring of knitting yarn)	2	3.1
Activities (IEAs)	Garments work (quality checker of clothes, monitoring of knitting yarn, etc.)	9	9.3

N.B.: Multiple responses

Case#2

Riajul Islam (12 years) said, *“My brother (18 years) went to Narayanganj in Dhaka to work after finishing his secondary examination. He also got admission to a government college in the nearby upazila. He is working there and sends some money to the family at the end of the month. When the examinations start, he will come home to take the exams.”* And

At a young age, children play a role in assisting their families by helping to mitigate the losses and damages caused by displacement, aiming to ensure a secure livelihood. Other members of households, such as uncles, aunts, grandmothers, grandfathers, nieces (daughters of siblings), and nephews (sons of siblings), also engage in these types of activities, or some of them, to cope with the losses caused by riverbank erosion displacement and to work towards mitigation and resilience.

Case#3

Farhana, who is 65 years old and a grandmother, said, *“The little girl helps her mother in cooking, plays with the boy on her mother’s lap, takes care of the child every day after coming home from school, collects hay from the neighbouring land and arranges it, and helps her mother with housework. Sometimes, when her mother goes out, she makes the bed and washes the clothes. By doing many small chores at home, the mother can use the time she has for other work.”*

7. Strategies for Reducing Vulnerability and Enhancing Resilience

The findings of the study indicate that the transportation and communication infrastructure in the study area is highly underdeveloped, with significant seasonal variations in modes of mobility. For instance, during the summer and winter seasons, residents are largely compelled to travel long distances on foot, whereas in the monsoon season, increased river water levels lead to greater reliance on boats for transportation.

This inadequate communication system has notable adverse implications for education. Children are often required to walk long distances (around 2 km) to reach their school, which contributes to reduced motivation and irregular attendance among students. Moreover, due to the fragile riverine geography and associated risks, many households are either unwilling or unable to consistently send their children to school. These challenges are further compounded by persistent economic constraints, collectively intensifying barriers to educational attainment. Consequently, the study underscores the critical importance of improving transportation and communication infrastructure in the *Char* region.

The study further reveals that approximately 79.4% of households are engaged in a single occupation. The lack of alternative skills significantly constrains income stability, particularly during off-seasons or periods of limited employment opportunities, resulting in heightened economic vulnerability. In this context, the study emphasises the importance of vocational training initiatives aimed at diversifying livelihood options. Such initiatives may include training in small-scale entrepreneurship, handicraft production, skill development in the use of modern equipment, and computer-based training, tailored to the interests and capacities of income-earning household members. These interventions have the potential to facilitate the development of a skilled and adaptable labour force.

In addition, the study highlights the potential for employment generation through subsidised investment in ecotourism by leveraging the natural scenic beauty of riverbank areas. To enhance economic self-

reliance among vulnerable households, the findings advocate for expanding the coverage and scale of existing social protection programs, alongside the formulation of dedicated policy measures for river erosion-affected and landless populations. Furthermore, the study stresses the need for permanent and sustainable solutions to riverbank erosion, the promotion of flood- and drought-resilient crop production, and the dissemination of these initiatives to the grassroots level through targeted subsidies to ensure effective implementation.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

Bangladesh is one of the most flood- and erosion-prone countries globally, with regions such as Bidyananda Union facing recurrent socio-economic and environmental stresses due to riverbank erosion. Erosion-induced displacement causes severe tangible losses, with homestead land, crops, trees, agricultural land, livestock, fishing grounds, roads, houses, furniture, and jewellery, as well as intangible consequences such as psychological distress, weakened social networks, loss of community cohesion, erosion of cultural heritage, and increased school dropouts. High illiteracy, dependence on agriculture, low income, and gendered caregiving responsibilities further exacerbate household vulnerability, limiting adaptive capacity. Household members (male, female, and children) employ various adaptive strategies, including extra time on agricultural and non-agricultural labour, animal husbandry, informal trade, family support, community engagement, and seeking temporary shelters or formal employment.

This study applies the Pressure and Release (PAR) model within the specific context of

riverbank erosion and Charland areas, illustrating how a single environmental hazard can intensify community-level vulnerability. The community-based recommendations suggested by the study offer practical guidance for policy formulation and development interventions in hazard-prone regions. However, the study is limited by its small geographic scope and sample size, suggesting the need for future research across larger areas with broader samples to enhance generalizability and policy relevance.

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Author Contribution

Md. Abu Saleh Shamim: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing- Original Draft, Visualisation; Shammy Islam: Supervision, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing- Review and Editing; Sezan Shaphique: Validation and Writing- Review and Editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest among them.

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